

Parallel Port Revival

Implementing a parallel port adapter using Arduino API-based and other contemporary software and PC interfaces

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Abstract

The classical parallel port interface used to provide an easy way to write or read digital in- and outputs (IOs) and thus to control peripheral electronic devices connected to a personal computer. Conventional modern computers do no longer provide such a simple hardware access. Here several alternatives are presented, allowing to access parallel port devices via USB, WiFi, Ethernet or Bluetooth.

Disclaimer: The hardware and software described here is not guaranteed to function and must not be applied if injuries or damage might result. Use it at your own risk!

1 Introduction

The parallel port (PP) interface was a de facto standard for all personal computers (PC) in the decades from 1980-2000 [1]. Figure 1 shows the corresponding DB-25 socket¹⁾ at the back of a PC together with other types. The pin layout is explained in Fig. 2. The PP is often called ‘Centronics interface’ and/or abbreviated as ‘LPT’ for Line Printer. Indeed, the PP was mostly used to connect printers, of which the first commonly available dot matrix variants were produced by the ‘Centronics Data Computer Corporation’. Nowadays the PP is standardized as ‘IEEE 1284’.

Figure 1: Rear side of PC from about 2010 with different connectors. The parallel port is shown in red.

Figure 2: Pin layout of a DB-25 PP socket (PC-side) [3].

Beyond the printer application the PP provides a simple interface from a host-PC to electronic

¹⁾ also called D-Sub 25, with 25 pins in a D-shaped metal shell; for details see reference [2].

devices which is ideal for ‘Maker’ projects. Starting with the canonical blinking LED one can turn a relay on or off, make a stepper motor rotate or check the status of temperature and humidity, or use it for various scientific purposes. In the following I focus on the non-printer applications.

A central part of this paper provides examples on how an interface from a host-PC to an electronic device can be designed. This interface allows a PC application to communicate program-controlled with a microcontroller. The PP-emulator presented in this paper is only one possible application based on this interface. The philosophy presented here differs from the often applied alternative use of microcontrollers, where the code is loaded into the microcontroller once and then you let it do the work.

The ease of use of the original PP incorporated into a PC is demonstrated by the simple output and input instructions. In BASIC, depending on the dialect, all PP interactions can be accomplished from a PC with PP interface through the following two commands:

```
OUT port-address, databyte
statusbyte = INP port-address
```

The first command sets the eight data line bits (forming one byte), thus sending data from the PC to the external device via the PP. This corresponds to the pins 2 – 9 of the PP connector. The port-address specifies the built-in parallel port interface to be used. With the second command the PC reads the 5 status bits from the device, as obtained from PP pins 10 (ACKnowledge), 11 (BUSY inverted), 12 (PAPER out), 13 (SELECT), and 15 (ERROR)²⁾.

Figure 3: PP output line drives an optocoupler for turning on or off an external load, here represented by the resistor $R4$.

The additional bidirectional 4 control lines of the PP are not discussed here. They are not necessary for simple communication purposes. Furthermore, most smaller boards for example from the Arduino series do not provide enough pins to serve more than 13 external connections. Analog values cannot be read or written by the PP.

The parallel port output data lines can deliver only currents of a few mA. That is enough

²⁾ Throughout this paper I use the abbreviations shown here in capital letters to denominate these status lines.

to drive an LED, but in general one needs an ‘amplifier’, for example in form of an external power supply and a transistor, in order to switch a relay or make a motor etc. run. To avoid undesired interference between the PP-emulator and the PP electronic device (PP-ED), the amplifier should be equipped with opto-isolators. In Fig. 3 such a circuit is sketched.

This paper does not cover the direct application of a PP interface by a microcontroller. Instead it discusses several methods on how to indirectly access a PP interface from a PC using a PP-emulator based on a microcontroller. To achieve this objective a microcontroller might be used for realizing the PC-PP interface, thus serving as a *PP-emulator* - but not more.

Cheap commercial USB to parallel adapter cables can only be used to address a line printer, but do not provide the full functionality of the parallel port [4, 5], therefore some efforts have to be made to obtain a PP-emulator.

Figure 4 illustrates the general functionality of a PP-emulator. The emulator is independent of the application applied on the PC. If the emulator, shown in green in the Figure, contains a microcontroller, it must be programmed – once and only once – before communication between PC and electronic device (ED) can start. From then on, we can regard the PP-emulator (hardware + uploaded software) as a black box.

Figure 4: PP-emulator as adapter between PC and PP-ED.

Why is the PP still of interest in times of high-performance processors, ubiquitous wireless communication and rapidly developing Artificial Intelligence technology?

- Because of the relative simplicity of communication between PC and electronic device through the PP interface, once this has been created.

- Since it provides a platform-independent standard to control IOs, to which no viable alternative exists so far.

Of course, each microcontroller can nowadays set and read some input-output lines. But the specifications (e.g. 5V versus 3.3V) and board layouts (e.g. pin configuration) differ from model to model. If one needs to use or develop a PP-ED device connected to a PC, together with the PC-ED control software, it should be possible to do it without having to refer to the intricacies of the microcontroller make. The PP-emulator should hide all these complications from the user.

The source code mentioned in this paper has been designed for deployment on UNIX operating systems. It is published on GitHub [6].

This paper is organized as follows: The next section gives an entry point to PP-emulators with a first practical example. The following section 3 discusses general aspects of PP-emulator projects. Subsequently several alternative PP-emulator realizations are presented, based on different microcontrollers, boards, interfaces (USB, WLAN, Ethernet, Bluetooth) and software. Eventually section 9 compares the characteristics of those PP-emulators in tabular form. Finally, I present a short summary.

2 PP-Emulator based on serial over USB

2.1 General setup

Typically, the first computer program starts with printing "Hello World", and the first successful operation of a PP-emulator shall be signaled by a blinking LED.

To achieve this, we need a computer with a USB interface, a test PP electronic device (called PP-ED for short, see Fig. 5) with an LED, and the PP-emulator itself.

On the other end we assume a computer (PC) running Linux³⁾. The C (C++) application code we would like to execute looks like

```
parallelport_out(1);  
sleep(1);  
parallelport_out(0);
```

to let the LED blink (once, for 1 second).

2.2 PP-Emulator hardware based on Arduino Nano

As adapter between PC and PP-ED I use a PP-emulator using a serial interface over USB as shown in Fig. 6. It uses an Arduino Nano development board, which is based on an ATmega328 microcontroller and uses a CH340 serial to USB transceiver⁴⁾

The 8 data lines and 5 status lines of the PP socket are connected to GPIO pins of the ATmega328.

³⁾ see section 2.6 regarding other operating systems

⁴⁾ Respective driver must be installed on host PC.

Figure 5: Very simple electronic setup for testing Parallel Port. The LED is connected to pin 2 (data line D0) and – via resistor – to pin 18 (GND). Since the PP interface uses TTL levels to define '0' and '1' ('Low' and 'High'), the corresponding voltages are near 5 V and require the resistor to limit the current through the LED.

In addition, ground (GND) of the Arduino board is connected to pins 18-25 of the PP socket. Not in the PP specifications but very practical for later tests of the inputs: the Arduino 5 V (VIN) line is coupled to the unused pin 1 of the PP (in the Centronics printer cable this the bidirectional STROBE line). It is convenient to supplement the interface with five 10 k Ω resistors, also shown in Fig. 6, to pull the PP status lines to ground. This ensures that unconnected input lines (ACK, BUSY, PAPER, SELECT, ERROR) are interpreted as logical '0'.

2.3 PP client application

The listing 1 shows a minimal version of a C++ program, `arduino_nano_usb_parallelport_minittest.cpp`, running on a Linux-PC, which is able to let the LED blink. It uses the `boost::asio` library [7] for the serial communication which must be available for compilation. If needed:

```
sudo apt install libboost-all-dev
```

2.3.1 Using the serial port

To simplify the code, the selection of the serial port is hard-coded⁵⁾.

The correct port can be determined by checking which port is enabled when plugging-in the PP-Emulator device.

One can check for newly added ports by comparing the output of

```
ls /dev/*
```

before and after attaching the device. Alternatively, one can inspect the output of

⁵⁾ specified at compile-time in contrast to at run-time

Figure 6: Prototype of a USB – Parallel Port interface (PP-emulator for short) based on an Arduino Nano (blue).

```
sudo dmesg
```

The correct path to the port must be used to define the C preprocessor macro `USBPORT` before compiling the example code!

Our program needs to access the USB port connected to the Arduino. This might at first not be permitted by the Linux operating system. The following command [8]

```
sudo usermod -a -G dialout $USER
```

admits the current user ‘dialout’ rights, i.e. USB access. Rebooting the operating system is most likely required to put this into effect.

Furthermore, on recent Linux distributions there is possibly a conflict with a Braille background process, `brltty` which makes the USB port connected to the Arduino disappear. This problem can be overcome with [9]

```
sudo ln -s /dev/null /etc/systemd/system/brltty-udev.service
```

The code in listing 1 comprises the function `parallelport_out.cpp` to talk to the USB port. The code is hopefully self-explanatory. Most important is the `boost::asio::write` statement in line 24, which addresses the Arduino of the PP-emulator. The $100\ \mu\text{s}$ sleep command ensures that consecutive port access instructions can be handled by the serial USB interface; in the main program of listing 1 a baud rate of 115200 has been selected.

Note: when using another microprocessor board, not an Arduino, or using WiFi=WLAN instead of USB, and correspondingly a different PP-emulator, only the header lines in the main program (listing 1) and the device specific instructions in `parallelport_out.cpp` (listing 1) need to be

```

1 //
2 // >>> arduino_nano_usb_parallelport_minittest.cpp <<< Thomas Hebbeker
3 //
4 #define USBPORT "/dev/ttyUSB0" // this needs to be adjusted
5
6 #include <iostream>
7 #include <unistd.h> // for sleep
8 #include <boost/asio.hpp> // for USB communication
9
10 using namespace std;
11
12 boost::asio::io_context io; // for setting up USB communication
13 boost::asio::serial_port port(io); // for setting up USB communication
14
15 void parallelport_out(int data) { // byte = 0 .. 255
16
17     const int pause_microseconds = 100;
18     string command;
19     string data_string;
20     int data_copy = data; // dont modify input to function
21
22     data_string = to_string(data_copy);
23     command = "D" + data_string + "\n";
24     boost::asio::write(port, boost::asio::buffer(command));
25     usleep(pause_microseconds); // not too fast....
26 }
27
28 int main()
29 {
30     port.open(USBPORT); // setting up USB communication
31     port.set_option(boost::asio::serial_port_base::baud_rate(115200));
32
33     sleep(7); // wait till arduino is ready after boot, in seconds
34
35     parallelport_out(1);
36     sleep(1);
37     parallelport_out(0);
38
39     port.close(); // for ending USB connection
40 }

```

Listing 1: Minimal C++ application *arduino_nano_usb_parallelport_minittest.cpp* for a blinking LED, using a serial interface. The function *parallelport_out.cpp* is used to address the output data lines of a PP via USB, for an Arduino Nano board. Some print statements and comment lines have been removed to make the listing leaner.

modified. The code written by the user, in our example the few lines near the end of the main program, does not have to be changed, it is universal – that is exactly what we want!

2.4 PP-Emulator firmware

The microcontroller used as the basis of the PP-emulator must be programmed to act as a USB-PP-emulator. This can be done with the help of any suitable computer, not necessarily the PC that is later used to run the PP client. Uploading the firmware is only necessary one time.

A convenient software package to program the microcontroller is the ‘Arduino IDE’ [10] under Linux, Windows and macOS.

Before getting at the code, we need to define which Arduino GPIO⁶⁾ pin is connected to which PP data bit or status bit. The chosen assignment is shown in Figure 7. Of course, also other ‘translation tables’ may be used. In any case, hardware and software have to match.

The listings 2 to 4 show the code that is used for the USB-PP-emulator discussed here. It is slightly simplified with respect to the full version in [6]. In `setup()` the pins used for data and status lines are configured, for example the last PP data line is matched with GPIO pin 9 on the Arduino Nano board. Note that `arduino_nano_usb_parallelport.ino` can also read the input status lines, not yet used in our simple blink-example.

Before the code can be uploaded via the Arduino IDE the board (Arduino Nano) and the USB port (for example `/dev/ttyUSB0`) must be specified. The processor must be ‘ATmega328P’. After successfully uploading the code, the Arduino IDE should be closed before running the test program of listing 1. The serial port is used for two different purposes, first for the programming of the PP-emulator and afterwards for the communication with the PP-emulator by programs running on the PC.

2.5 Reading status lines

While the Arduino code presented foresees that the status lines can be read via PC, we have not yet tested this feature. Fig. 8 shows another minimalistic PP-ED serving as PP tester: Apart from the LED, a button is added, connected to Pin 10 of the PP socket, which is the ACK line, and to GND. The 100 k Ω resistor connected to GND pulls ACK to low if the button is not pushed. While pressing the button ACK is connected to the 5 V taken via PP pin 1 from the PP-emulator, and thus becomes high.

The firmware source file `arduino_nano_usb_parallelport.ino` in listings 2 to 4 is already prepared for reading input status bits. On the client side one must extend the test program and supplement the `parallelport_out` code by a `parallelport_in` function. The complete listing/source code can be found in GitHub [6]. The salient lines for the calling main test program are:

```
status = parallelport_in();  
ACK = status & 0b00001;
```

which reads all five status lines and extracts the ACK bit. Inside `parallelport_in` one finds:

⁶⁾ General Purpose Input Output

parallel port data lines:

```
-----  
arduino board pins      => parallel port = PP  
D2 = Pin 2              => Data out bit 0   Pin 2  
D3 = Pin 3              => Data out bit 1   Pin 3  
D4 = Pin 4              => Data out bit 2   Pin 4  
D5 = Pin 5              => Data out bit 3   Pin 5  
D6 = Pin 6              => Data out bit 4   Pin 6  
D7 = Pin 7              => Data out bit 5   Pin 7  
D8 = Pin 8              => Data out bit 6   Pin 8  
D9 = Pin 9              => Data out bit 7   Pin 9
```

note: can't use D0 and D1 since they are used by UART - USB communication

parallel port status lines:

```
-----  
arduino board pins      <= parallel port = PP  
A0 = Pin 14             <= Data in bit 6   Pin 10  ACK  
A1 = Pin 15             <= Data in bit 7   Pin 11  BUSY inverted  
A2 = Pin 16             <= Data in bit 5   Pin 12  PAPER (_END)  
A3 = Pin 17             <= Data in bit 4   Pin 13  SELECT  
A4 = Pin 18             <= Data in bit 3   Pin 15  ERROR
```

In addition, the following hardware connections are needed:

```
GND(Arduino)           = GND(PP) (lines 18-25)  
VIN = 5V (Arduino)     = pin 1 (PP) = Strobe (inverted)
```

Pull-down resistors to GND of 10 kOhm for the lines A0 - A4 are optional.

Figure 7: Arduino Nano - Parallel Port connections.

```

1
2 // >>> arduino_nano_usb_parallelport.ino <<<      T.Hebbeker
3
4 String inputString = "";      // a String to hold incoming data
5 bool stringComplete = false; // whether the string is complete
6 String outputString = "";    // a String to hold outgoing data
7
8 const int high = 1;
9 const int low = 0;
10
11 int databyte;
12 int statusbyte;
13
14 const int GPIO_data_line[8] = {2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9};
15 const int GPIO_status_line[5] = {14,15,16,17,18};
16
17 int bit[8];
18 static int oldbit[8] = {-1,-1,-1,-1,-1,-1,-1,-1};
19
20 int factor;
21
22 // for on-board built-in LED
23 const int builtin_led = 13;
24
25 void serialEvent() {
26     while (Serial.available()) {
27         // get the new byte:
28         char inChar = (char)Serial.read();
29         // add it to the inputString:
30         inputString += inChar;
31         // if the incoming character is a newline, set a flag so the main loop
           can
32         // do something about it:
33         if (inChar == '\n') {
34             stringComplete = true;
35         }
36     }
37 }

```

Listing 2: Arduino code *arduino_nano_usb_parallelport.ino* to provide the USB ↔ PP interface. Part I. The serialEvent function is copied from [11].

```

1 void setup() {
2
3   // for USB communication
4   Serial.begin(115200); // default = standard = well tested
5
6   // reserve 200 bytes for the inputString:
7   inputString.reserve(200);
8
9   // prepare builtin LED
10  pinMode(builtin_led, OUTPUT);
11
12  // prepare GPIOs for data lines
13  // and set everything to low
14  for(int i=0; i<8; i++) {
15    pinMode(GPIO_data_line[i], OUTPUT);
16    digitalWrite(GPIO_data_line[i], low);
17  }
18
19  // prepare GPIOs for status lines
20  for(int i=0; i<5; i++) {
21    pinMode(GPIO_status_line[i], INPUT);
22  }
23
24  // say hello upon startup
25  delay(1000); // microseconds
26  for(int m=1; m<=5; m++) {
27    digitalWrite(builtin_led, high);
28    delay(300);
29    digitalWrite(builtin_led, low);
30    delay(300);
31  }
32 }

```

Listing 3: Arduino code *arduino_nano_usb_parallelport.ino* to provide the USB ↔ PP interface. Part II.

```

1 void loop() {
2
3   if (stringComplete) {
4
5     // get data from PC
6     if(inputString.substring(0,1) == "D") {
7
8       databyte = inputString.substring(1,8).toInt();
9
10      for(int i=0; i<8; i++) {
11        bit[i] = ((databyte >> i) & 0x01);
12      }
13
14      for(int i=0; i<8; i++) {
15        if(bit[i]!=oldbit[i]) {
16          oldbit[i]=bit[i];
17          digitalWrite(GPIO_data_line[i],bit[i]);
18        }
19      }
20
21    }
22
23    // send status data to PC
24    if(inputString.substring(0,1) == "S") {
25
26      factor = 1;
27      statusbyte = 0;
28      for(int i=0; i<5; i++) {
29        bit[i] = digitalRead(GPIO_status_line[i]);
30        statusbyte = statusbyte + bit[i]*factor;
31        factor = factor*2;
32      }
33
34      statusbyte = statusbyte + 10; // guarantees 2 characters
35      outputString = String(statusbyte);
36      Serial.print(outputString);
37
38    }
39
40    inputString = "";
41    stringComplete = false;
42
43  } // end StringComplete
44
45 } // end loop

```

Listing 4: Arduino code *arduino_nano_usb_parallelport.ino* to provide the USB ↔ PP interface. Part III.

Figure 8: Rudimentary setup to test both output and input of a Parallel Port slave device.

```
command = "S\n";
boost::asio::write(port, boost::asio::buffer(command));
boost::asio::read(port, boost::asio::buffer(&c_from_arduino,2));
statusbyte = stoi(&c_from_arduino) - 10;
return statusbyte;
```

The third line reads always 2 characters, since in the arduino firmware the output is increased by 10, thus here we find values between $0 + 10 = 10$ and $2^5 - 1 + 10 = 31 + 10 = 41$. In the fourth line this offset is removed.

2.6 Tipps and Tricks

- The firmware *arduino_nano_usb_parallelport.ino* can be tested easily without using a C++ program. A shell command like

```
echo "D255" > /dev/ttyUSB0
```

sends characters to the USB port `/dev/ttyUSB0`. In this example it turns all 8 data lines on. To make this work, the correct baud rate has to be set first:

```
stty -F /dev/ttyUSB0 115200
```

For an Arduino Nano⁷⁾ a reset/reboot of the board when addressing it via the USB port has to be prevented. This can be accomplished by connecting one of the reset pins to the 3.3 V line. Attention, please: This connection prevents uploading a program to the Arduino, e.g. from the Arduino IDE. If this is necessary, the cable must be removed. Elegant solution: a jumper on the board...

- As alternative to the `boost::asio` library one can use system commands inside C++ code to address the PP-emulator, of the form

⁷⁾ and also Arduino Uno, but not for a NodeMCU or ESP32 development boards

```
string command = "echo_D" + data_string + "_>_/dev/ttyUSB0";
system(command.c_str());
```

where `data_string` contains the byte defining the setting of the data lines, for example '255' will pull all lines to high.

- For other Arduino boards most of the software presented here can be reused. One has to check which pins are available without constraints, see also discussion in the following sections.
- The firmware lets an LED blink five times when booting. This helps in verifying that the board is 'alive'. Furthermore, it can indicate which code is uploaded, in particular the sequence identifies which interface between PP-emulator and PC is used: 5 blink cycles = USB, 6 = WLAN, 7 = Ethernet, 8 = Bluetooth. This becomes very useful if one board like the ESP32 development board presented in section 7 offers several alternative interfaces, and if each of them needs its own code. One can thus recognize easily during boot which code is running – by counting LED blinks.
- The USB port name in the C++ code must be adapted 'by hand' to the one used on your PC to address the PP-Emulator. To find out which ports are available the source code *enumerateTtyDevices.cpp* may be used [6].
- The behavior of the board can be simulated with Wokwi [12]. In section 7 and in particular in Fig. 13 I present an example.
- Running the C++ code to address the PP-emulator on a windows PC? This is possible, please follow these instructions:
 - Install a WSL-2⁸⁾ environment under Windows 11. It provides Linux like terminal windows.
 - Open a WSL-2 terminal window
 - Install a C++ compiler: `sudo apt install gcc`
 - Install the BOOST ASIO library: `sudo apt install libboost-all-dev`
Make sure you get a recent version, else the following will not work.
 - The more tricky part: You need to enable USB access from a WSL-2 shell. Follow the instructions in ref. [13]; it shows how to use the `usbipd-win` software to obtain USB-access. With the PP-emulator connected: Check if you can see the USB port via `ls /dev/*`
 - Compile and execute the C++ program.

Of course, there are also other compilers available on Windows, and one might want to include a Graphical User Interface (GUI). But such considerations are beyond the scope of this paper.

⁸⁾ Windows Subsystem for Linux

3 Possible variants

Before setting up a PP-emulator, we need to identify available hard- and software on the PC side and match those to the requirements on the PP-ED end.

Table 1 presents possible combinations of PC hardware and interfaces connected to a potential PP-emulator. Some even allow for a direct PP interface.

computer	operating system	interface	PP-emulator	PP speed
desktop PC	Windows, Apple, Linux	PP via PCI card	not needed	> 100 kHz
high end Raspb. Pi	Raspberry Pi OS, Linux	PP via GPIO pins	not needed	> 1000 kHz
PC/notebook/RPi	various	USB	e.g. Arduino	1 kHz
PC/notebook/RPi	various	Ethernet	Arduino+Shield	1 kHz
PC/notebook/RPi	various	WLAN	e.g. ESP8266	100 Hz
PC/notebook/RPi	various	Bluetooth	e.g. ESP32	10 Hz

Table 1: Possible realizations of a parallel port interface and expected performance.

Some comments are in order:

- The high end Raspberry Pi (e.g. RPi 4 or RPi 5) is supposed to be used as a desktop computer with monitor, keyboard etc. Since it has many GPIOs (General Purpose Input/Output) pins, they can be interpreted as PP data and status lines.
- A low end Raspberry Pi (Pico), a microprocessor, can take the role of a PP-emulator.
- The speed estimate given corresponds to the number of PP commands addressing the data lines that can be executed per time interval.
- The advantages of the wireless solutions are clear: no cable is needed, with WiFi or Ethernet one can even access the PP-ED from anywhere in the world. However, the performance in terms of speed is modest.
- While the microprocessor boards discussed here (like Arduino developing kits with ATMEL processor) act as a ‘dumb’ USB-PP translation engine, one could also use them for ‘outsourcing’ tasks from the PC to the microprocessor. An example is a stepper motor driver, which involves a rapid switching between High and Low on several data lines.
- Finally – after code development on the PC – one might conclude that a microprocessor-based PP-emulator can be used standalone to address the PP – also this is fine, and does not require any changes on the PP-ED side.

Obviously, this paper cannot describe solutions to all combinations which table 1 provides. I rather use examples to demonstrate different ways of achieving an emulation of a PP interface.

What are the requirements at the PP-ED end? The important keywords are

- cable or wireless
- speed

- compatibility with available PC hard- and software
- simplicity and cost of PP-emulator

Depending on these needs at least one of the projects presented in the previous or following sections should offer a solution.

4 Going wireless

4.1 WiFi PP-emulator based on NodeMCU ESP8266

Figure 9: Prototype of a WiFi based Parallel Port interface, PP-emulator for short, based on an ESP8266 board.

This gadget is shown in Fig. 9. It is built around the affordable microcontroller development board NodeMCU ESP8266 E12 which offers WiFi [14]. The wiggly lines on the board represent the antenna. It uses as eight data lines the GPIOs 16, 1, 3, 0, 2, 14, 12 and 13, the five input status bits correspond to pins 15, 4, 5, 10 and A0 (see below).

The advantages of a PP connection with a wireless interface are obvious! The price to pay is (s)low performance and the requirement of a WiFi network, which must not only exist but must also be accessible, which means router name and password need to be known. The setup described in the following uses the ESP8266 as a WiFi host controller, which connects to the PC via a router. The PC is independently connected to the same router, via WLAN or Ethernet. In principle one can access such a PP-emulator from anywhere in the world, but I will not discuss this aspect here.

Evidently the ESP8266 board needs to be connected to an external power supply or to a USB port of the host PC - using this exclusively as power supply but not for communication – only

when the firmware is uploaded.

This board delivers output voltages of 3.3 V on the GPIO output lines. And it does not accept (much) higher voltages on the GPIO inputs.

This implies that the input voltages delivered by the PP status lines should be lowered from 5 V to about 3.4 V, which the ESP8266 can handle. For each input I thus reduce the 5 V expected to come from PP status lines to

$$\frac{R_1}{R_1 + R_2} \cdot 5 \text{ V} = 3.4 \text{ V}$$

with a voltage divider using $R_1 = 470 \Omega$ and $R_2 = 220 \Omega$. Some of these resistors are visible in Fig. 9. Other suitable combinations are the pairs $R_1 = 390 \Omega$ plus $R_2 = 220 \Omega$ and $R_1 = 470 \Omega$ plus $R_2 = 270 \Omega$, both resulting in 3.2 V. If the resulting voltage is lower, the circuit might not work if the input voltage is 3.3 V instead of 5 V, The resistance values have not been optimized, possibly overall higher values, with the same input voltage reduction factor, will also do the job.

As for the Arduino Board I connect the 5 V coming from the USB cable to the (otherwise unused) STROBE pin of the PP.

The exact pin translation table is shown in the GitHub repository [6]. The challenge here is that the number of GPIOs that can be used freely as input or output is limited and one has to ‘fight’ to get all 8 data plus 5 status lines of the PP interface served.

4.2 ESP8266 coding

As for the Arduino Nano, the ESP8266 needs to get the proper firmware in order to make it perform as PP-emulator. One can again use the Arduino IDE package, but now the board to be selected is a ‘generic ESP8266 module’. If this selection is not possible, the IDE must get an appropriate add-on [15]. Note that in the boardmanager possibly an older version of the library ‘ESP8266 Boards’ must be selected; for my NodeMCU development board version 2.7.4. did the job. The ESP8266 firmware *esp8266_wlan_parallelport.ino* is then uploaded via USB (!). It is similar to the Arduino code as shown in listings 2 to 4, but there are salient differences since finally the access to the PP will not use the USB port but WiFi=WLAN. At the beginning we need:

```
#include <ESP8266WiFi.h>
#define STASSID "WiFi-2.4-9876" // local WiFi network, to be adapted
#define STAPSK "12345" // password, to be adapted
const char* ssid = STASSID;
const char* password = STAPSK;
// Create an instance of the server, specify the port to listen on
WiFiServer server(80);
```

Then, inside setup() the server must be started and the GPIO pins defined, in this simplified example just one for data line output and one for status line input:

```
WiFi.mode(WIFI_STA);
WiFi.begin(ssid, password);
// Start the server
server.begin();
```

```

// define pins
const int GPIO_D = 16;
const int GPIO_S = 15;
pinMode(GPIO_D, OUTPUT);
pinMode(GPIO_S, INPUT);

```

A more complete version, *esp8266_wlan_parallelport.ino* can be found in [6]. Inside the loop() those pins can be set or read via

```

WiFiClient client = server.available();
if (!client) return;
client.setTimeout(1000); // in milliseconds
// Read the first line of the request
String req = client.readStringUntil('\r');
if (req.indexOf(F("/D0")) != -1) digitalWrite(GPIO_D, low);
if (req.indexOf(F("/D1")) != -1) digitalWrite(GPIO_D, high);
if (req.indexOf(F("/S")) != -1) val_S = digitalRead(GPIO_S);

```

The last three lines define the commands (D0,D1,S) to be sent to the ESP8266. The complete code is available from GitHub [6]. A simple test from a PC terminal looks like this:

```
curl http://192.168.1.49/D1
```

It is based on the curl software [16] which can be installed via

```

sudo apt install curl
sudo apt-get install libcurl4-openssl-dev

```

The example IP address 192.168.1.49 must be adapted, of course. How can one find out the IP address the router is using to connect to the ESP8266 board? A terminal shell command like

```
arp -a | grep ESP
```

gives the answer. However, this works only once the esp8266 has been addressed from the PC. By first issuing the command

```
fping -q -a -s -g 192.168.1.0/24
```

all possible IP addresses are ‘touched’ and subsequently the arp command works⁹⁾.

4.3 A modified test program

The C++ test program, *esp8266_wlan_parallelport_minittest.cpp* will look similar to listing 1. but I need to define the IP address, for example

```
#define IPADDRESS "http://192.168.1.49/"
```

The functions *parallelport_out* as shown in listing 1 and *parallelport_in* as described in section 2 must be modified, too; I need here the curl library for the WiFi access. The slightly simplified

⁹⁾ In general, both arp and fping need to be installed first: `sudo apt install net-tools`, `sudo apt install fping`.

code *paralleport.out* is shown in listing 5. Compilation of a test program (in this example with the GNU compiler) requires the inclusion of the curl library:

```
g++ -o paralleport_test.exe paralleport_test.cpp -curl
```

```
1 #include <curl/curl.h>
2
3 static size_t WriteCallback(void *contents, size_t size,
4     size_t nmemb, void *userp) {
5     ((string*)userp)->append((char*)contents, size * nmemb);
6     return size * nmemb;
7 }
8 static int fcall = 0;
9
10 void paralleport_out(int data) { // byte = 0 .. 255
11
12     CURL *curl;
13     CURLcode res;
14     const int pause_microseconds = 100;
15     int data_copy = data; // dont modify input to function
16     string command;
17     string data_string;
18     string readBuffer;
19     const char* ipaddress = "http://192.168.1.49/"; // adapt !
20     string ip;
21     ip = ipaddress;
22
23     curl = curl_easy_init();
24
25     if(curl) {
26         data_string = to_string(data_copy);
27         command = ip + "D" + data_string;
28         curl_easy_setopt(curl, CURLOPT_URL, command.c_str());
29         curl_easy_setopt(curl, CURLOPT_WRITEFUNCTION, WriteCallback);
30         curl_easy_setopt(curl, CURLOPT_WRITEDATA, &readBuffer);
31         res = curl_easy_perform(curl);
32         usleep(pause_microseconds); // not too fast....
33         curl_easy_cleanup(curl);
34     }
35 }
```

Listing 5: Function *paralleport.out.cpp* to address the output data lines of a PP via WLAN, for a NodeMCU ESP8266 board.

Note that since the number of GPIO pins of the NodeMCU ESP8266 board is limited, a couple of restrictions is to be observed: some pins are reserved for the serial interface via USB, others are High during boot etc. [17].

As a consequence of these constraints the ESP8266 code *esp8266_wlan_paralleport.ino* uses also the analog ADC input, with statements like

```
int adcvalue_threshold = 64; // corresponds to about 1/4 of 3.3 V
```

```
int statusbit = 0;
int adcvalue = analogRead(A0);
if (adcvalue > adcvalue_threshold) statusbit = 1;
```

Secondly, during boot up of the ESP8266 some data lines are High, which might cause unwanted effects. In principle, also the USB port can be used to address the ESP8266, acting as PP-emulator, in a similar fashion as the Arduino Nano. However, now two lines, TX and RX (GPIO1 and GPIO3), needed for the serial interface via USB, become unavailable. Thus, this is not a practical option.

After all, the newer, bigger and more powerful ESP32, presented in section 7, is the better choice for most applications. However, the cheap EPS8266 is wide-spread and I want to point out in this paper how to deal with limitations such as the relatively small number of GPIO pins.

In a WSL-2 shell under Windows 11 the C++ code presented here [6] can be used, too. Once the curl software [16] is installed, commands like

```
curl http://192.168.1.49/D1          IP address to be adapted!
```

work immediately.

5 Raspberry Pi Pico with Python Interpreter

Here I make use of a low-end Raspberry Pi board, the Raspberry Pico. It plays in the same league – concerning both functionality and form factor – as the Arduino Nano and ESP8266 boards. Also in this application I use the USB interface for PP access, but the software strategy is quite different. I do not transfer a user made program developed especially for the PP access to the Pico, but rather upload a wide-spread general-purpose Python interpreter called MicroPython [18]. So, the PP user has not to do anything special on the Pico side.

A C++ program running on the PC then sends tiny bits of Python code to the Raspberry Pico board, via USB serial communication. An example is *pin6on.py*:

```
from machine import Pin
gpiopin = Pin(6,Pin.OUT)
gpiopin.value(1)
```

which sets Pin 6 to High. The adafruit-ampy library [19] can be used for the transfer of this code from the PC to the Pico, with a Linux command like

```
ampy --port /dev/ttyACM0 run pin6on.py
```

where */dev/ttyACM0* specifies the USB port used in this example. The python script gets immediately executed on the Pico board. In C++ code this can be realized with a system call. The details can be found in [6]. To obtain the ampy library one needs python3 on the PC and the following commands must be issued:

```
sudo apt install python3-pip
sudo pip3 install adafruit-ampy
```

A similar library is called `mremote` [20]. It finds the correct USB port automatically, and can also be used to execute a python script residing on the Raspberry Pico board. After installation with

```
sudo pip3 install mremote
```

a terminal command may look like

```
mremote run pin6on.py
```

This executes the python script `pin6on.py` stored on the PC. It can also be copied to the Pico board with

```
mremote cp pin6on.py :pin6on.py
```

and subsequently always executed locally on the Pico, initiated with the PC command

```
mremote exec "import pin6on"
```

This is the faster alternative!

To read data from the Pico is a bit more tricky: the C++ statement

```
FILE *stdout_pico = freopen("stdout_file.txt", "wb", stdout);
```

redirects the standard output (often addressed via `cout` commands). The Pico then writes to the file `stdout_file.txt` on the PC! The MicroPython code

```
from machine import Pin
gpiopin = Pin(20, Pin.IN)
print(gpiopin.value())
```

interpreted by the Pico reads the status of pin 20 – used as input – and prints the corresponding bit to `stdout_file.txt`. The code running on the PC does produce some non-fatal error messages, which can be ignored.

This software arrangement is quite clumsy and the execution of a PP command very sluggish – it takes of the order of half a second. But the programming is simple and straightforward, and for many ‘slow control’ applications the speed is not an issue.

Figure 10 shows a prototype board. It uses as eight data lines the GPIOs 2, 3, 6, 7, 10, 11, 14 and 15. The five input status bits correspond to pins 18 to 22. Resistor pairs of $R_1 = 47\text{ k}\Omega$ and $R_2 = 22\text{ k}\Omega$ ensure that unconnected inputs are interpreted as Low and a voltage of 5 V is reduced to 3.4 V.

Also under Windows 11 the Raspberry Pico works as PP-emulator. Of course, one needs to install `mremote` [20] or `ampy` [19] first, and one must permit access to the USB port from a WSL-2 shell [13].

Alternatively, one can also upload the C++ code [6] `raspberry_pico_usb_parallelport.ino` via the Arduino IDE to the Raspberry Pico if one takes care of some peculiarities of this board [21]. Then it can be addressed via functions `parallelport_out` and `parallelport_in` as displayed in listing 1 and described in section 2. Thus, it uses the `boost::asio` library [7]. This works very well, and a high speed can be achieved, as Table 2 quantifies. Thus the MicroPython based software setup described above is more of a curiosity and rarely a practical solution.

Figure 10: Prototype of a Raspberry Pico used as PP-emulator.

6 The IO-Warrior does it all

6.1 PP access via IO-Warrior28

The universal I/O board IO-Warrior28 does not need any programming [22]. It can be directly used as a PP-emulator, one only needs to cable it up properly. Figure 11 shows the resulting prototype. Of the three GPIO ports of the IO-Warrior28 with up to 8 channels each I use port 1 (P1.0 – P1.7) for the PP data lines and port P0.2 – port P0.6 for the status lines. The board is connected via USB to a PC.

Some resistors are needed to make it work as desired: Internally the output lines are equipped with pull-up resistors of about $40\text{ k}\Omega$. This implies that even low-current LEDs cannot be lit. Therefore, for each of the 8 used output lines an external $1\text{ k}\Omega$ pull-up resistor is added, it connects the output to the 3.3 V .

While the IO-Warrior28 is powered via the 5 V from the USB cable, it uses internally only 3.3 V . This implies that the input voltages delivered by the PP status lines should be reduced from 5 V to about 3.4 V , as we have seen before for the NodeMCU ESP8266. I opted here for similar resistor pairs, of $4.7\text{ k}\Omega$ and $2.2\text{ k}\Omega$ for each of the five used IO-Warrior input lines. These voltage dividers adjust the voltage level and furthermore pull the input lines to ground while unused.

6.2 Code for IO-Warrior28

As underlined before, this board cannot be programmed and it does not need to be programmed. But we need some C code to access the PP via an IO-Warrior28 from a PC. The manufacturer, Code Mercenaries, supplies a Software Development Kit (SDK) for Linux, macOS and

Figure 11: Prototype of an IO-Warrior28 based Parallel Port interface.

Windows [22]; the language is C, not C++. It includes – among other code elements – the functions `ReadSimpleNonBlocking` and `WriteSimple` to access the GPIO pins. These are part of the test and example program `iowkittest.c`, which is included in the SDK. I use the Linux flavor and transform the supplied `iowkittest.c` to act as a test program for the IO-Warrior28 PP interface. Installation of the resulting code, `iowarrior_usb_parallelport_minitest.c` is done via the (adapted) Makefile provided also by the company. Furthermore, the file `iowkittest.Po` in subdirectory `.deps` must be modified. Execution of the PP emulator program on a PC requires administrator privileges:

```
sudo iowarrior_usb_parallelport_minitest.exe
```

The USB port does not need to be specified by the user, the IO-Warrior28 shows automatically up under

```
/dev/usb/iowarrior*
```

The code for `iowarrior_usb_parallelport_minitest.c` and the functions `iowarrior_usb_parallelport_in.c` and `iowarrior_usb_parallelport_out.c` can be downloaded from GitHub [6]. The following listings 6, 7 and 8 show the core part of the test program and the output and input functions.

7 Bluetooth

The ESP32 is the bigger brother/sister of the ESP8266 introduced earlier. Many versions exist, I use here a 38-pin board with the CP2102 serial controller. WiFi and Bluetooth are on-board. The latter is offered both in form of the classical/legacy version 4.2 and also as BLE – which stands for Low Energy and uses a different protocol. Here I go for the legacy version. Another

```

1  ...
2  #include "iowarrior_usb_parallelport_out.c"
3  #include "iowarrior_usb_parallelport_in.c"
4
5  int main(int argc, char *argv[])
6  {
7      int status;
8      int i;
9      int numIows;
10     IOWKIT_HANDLE devHandle;
11
12     // Open device
13     devHandle = IowKitOpenDevice();
14     if (devHandle == NULL)
15     {
16         printf("Failed to open device\n");
17         goto out;
18     }
19
20     // Get number of IOWs in system
21     numIows = IowKitGetNumDevs();
22
23     // Get all IOW handles
24     for (i = 0; i < numIows; i++)
25     {
26         // Get device handle and init object
27         iows[i] = IowKitGetDeviceHandle(i + 1);
28         IowKitSetWriteTimeout(iows[i], 1000);
29         IowKitSetTimeout(iows[i], 2000);
30     }
31
32     // set GPIOs to 1 - that means can use them as inputs!
33     WriteSimple(iows[0], 0xFFFF00FF); // spare port 1 = data lines
34
35     printf("_Here_comes_the_blink_test:_\n");
36     parallelport_out(1);
37     sleep(3);
38     parallelport_out(0);
39     printf("_LED_blink_test_completed_\n");
40
41     printf("\n_Next_I_check_out_the_status_line_ACK._\n");
42     printf("_Press_the_corresponding_button_(you_got_5_seconds)_.\n");
43     sleep(5);
44     status = parallelport_in();
45     int ACK = status & 0b00001;
46     printf("_Status_line_read._ACK_=_%d_\n\n", ACK);
47
48     // Close device
49     IowKitCloseDevice(devHandle);
50     out:
51     return 0;
52 }

```

Listing 6: Program *iowarrior_usb_parallelport_minittest.c* to address the output data lines of a PP via USB through an IO-Warrior28 (Only parallelport related code is shown, remainder like in *iowkittest.c*).

```

1 void paralleport_out(int data) { // byte = 0 .. 255
2
3     DWORD value;
4
5     // need to shift bits
6     value = data << 8;
7
8     // set iowarrior output bits    port 1!
9     WriteSimple(iows[0], value);
10
11     return;
12 }

```

Listing 7: Function *paralleport_out.cpp* to address the output data lines of a PP via USB through an IO-Warrior28 (simplified version).

```

1 int paralleport_in() {
2
3     ULONG rc;
4     IOWKIT56_IO_REPORT rep56;
5
6     static int statusbyte = 0; // static since iowarrior reacts only to
7     changes !
8     int imax = 50; // maximum number of read iterations.
9     for (int i = 1; i <= imax; i++) // repeat to catch all status line
10     changes
11     {
12         rc = ReadSimpleNonBlocking(iows[0], &rep56); // this detects CHANGES
13         of status lines
14         if (rc)
15         {
16             // here I need only the first Byte:
17             statusbyte = rep56.Bytes[0];
18             // and I filter out only bits numbers 2 - 6
19             statusbyte = statusbyte & 0x7C;
20             // and I shift back to bits 0 - 4:
21             statusbyte = statusbyte/4;
22         }
23         else {
24             break;
25         }
26     }
27     return statusbyte;
28 }

```

Listing 8: Function *paralleport_in.cpp* to read the status lines of a PP via USB through an IO-Warrior28 (simplified version).

advantage of the ESP32 compared to the ESP8266 is the larger number of GPIO pins, so that 8+5 PP lines can be identified easily, without suffering from the constraints described above for the ESP8266.

The only disadvantages of the ESP32 controller are its larger physical size, its higher price and the smaller WiFi antenna, which might lead to a reduced range or reliability, if no external antenna is used.

Figure 12: Prototype of a Bluetooth – Parallel Port interface making use of an ESP32 board.

The corresponding PP-emulator is shown in Fig. 12. This board delivers output voltages of 3.3 V on the GPIO output lines. And it does not accept (much) higher voltages on the GPIO inputs. As voltage dividers I use resistor pairs as described above for the ESP8266 board, but I chose higher values of $R_1 = 47\text{ k}\Omega$ and $R_2 = 22\text{ k}\Omega$. Some of these resistors are visible in Fig. 9.

As for the Arduino Board I connect the 5 V coming from the USB cable to the (otherwise unused) STROBE pin of the PP.

To access the ESP32 via Bluetooth, it needs to be coupled to the PC, using the command

```
sudo rfcomm bind /dev/rfcomm0 D8:BC:38:E6:23:76 1
```

The MAC address (Media Access Control) uniquely identifies a board, and naturally the example given above has to be adapted. To find ‘your’ MAC address please try the command

```
hcitool | grep ESP
```

This tool is part of the blueZ package that can be installed via

```
sudo apt install bluez*
```

7.1 ESP32 coding

For Bluetooth access the code to be uploaded to the board resembles the firmware for the USB access via Arduino Nano. Instead of initializing the USB-serial interface with

```
Serial.begin(115200);
```

the Bluetooth communication is started via

```
SerialBT.begin("ESP32_parallelport");
```

Subsequently the commands *digitalWrite* and *digitalRead* to access the GPIO pins can be used as before.

On the PC side one can access the ESP32 board with a shell command like

```
echo "D123" >/dev/rfcomm0
```

The functions *esp32_bluetooth_parallelport_in.cpp* and *esp32_bluetooth_parallelport_out.cpp* use system calls to send *echo* commands to the ESP32 board via Bluetooth. To read the status lines, the ESP32 writes via a command like

```
SerialBT.write(statusbit);
```

to *stdout*. These data can be intercepted by the PC C++ program by redirecting it to a file. The details are given in GitHub [6].

The ESP32 can also be programmed to be used as USB or WiFi PP-emulator. The corresponding code and the performance are close to those for the ESP8266 NodeMCU described above. Independent of interface, the ESP32 has enough GPIO pins so that the problems of the ESP8266 in this respect can all be avoided.

7.2 Wokwi simulation

For rapid prototyping a simulation of the embedded device can be beneficial to reduce the feedback time.

I have experimented with the simulator Wokwi [12]. It is a simple, limited and easy to use tool to simulate program execution on hand-picked development boards in combination with some electronic components. The tool can be used via its website or as Visual Studio Code [23] extension.

Wokwi supports among others the “ESP32-DevKitC V4” and “Arduino Uno R3” development boards. Fig. 13 illustrates a simulation of an ESP32 development board, inputs are connected to a DIP switch and outputs to an LED bar.

Apart from interacting with the simulated accessory electronic components, one can connect to the development board via simulated WiFi (where applicable) or serial line. I have tested the complete PP-emulator system on a PC.

The setup is sketched in Fig. 14. The PP-emulator client application communicates via a serial line device. That is a relay to the TCP server provided by the simulator which in turn relays the communication to the serial interface of the simulated microprocessor.

Figure 13: Circuit Diagram of Wokwi-Simulation of ESP32 as PP-emulator. On the left one recognizes the five status lines (inputs), on the right side the eight data lines (output) are shown.

Figure 14: Testing the PP-emulator system on a PC

The advantages of such a simulation are obvious: One can design and debug both hardware and software without ordering electronics parts or touching a soldering iron. Furthermore, the setup gets nicely documented, see Fig. 13.

8 Ethernet

A simple Arduino like board with an Ethernet adapter was not available. However, one can plug an Ethernet shield for example onto an Arduino Uno board [24]. Figure 15 shows such an arrangement, supplemented with a parallel port interface.

In principle the same pin configuration as described for the Arduino Nano above can be used – with the exception of GPIO line 4 which is no longer 'free'. Instead GPIO 19 is used as an output.

The Arduino-Ethernet pair can be operated in a similar fashion as the ESP8266 or ESP32 with WLAN interface: the board serves as a Web-server which connects to a router. While in the former examples this is achieved via WiFi, now a standard RJ-45 Ethernet cable is used between board and router. And the Arduino needs to get power, for example via its USB interface. On the PC/notebook side the board is accessed through the router, by connecting PC with router through another Ethernet RJ-45 cable or via WLAN. As communication software again the curl package is used. Thus *curl* commands like

```
curl http://192.168.1.199/D255
```

issued from a terminal shell will work here, too. The IP address as defined in *arduino_ethernet_parallelport.ino* has to be used.

An alternative way to communicate is a direct RJ-45 Ethernet cable connecting PC/notebook to the Arduino-Ethernet board. This requires a special ethernet configuration [25]. The expected advantage is a high-speed data transfer between the two partners, however this hope does not come true, see table below.

9 Comparison of PP-emulators

Table 2 summarizes the results of benchmark tests to evaluate the speed for commands addressing the data lines and status lines. To test the speed either only write or only read commands were sent, inside a loop with a high loop count n . The corresponding execution time t was measured. For the write statements the 8 data bits were chosen as $\text{mod}(i, 256)$ with the incrementing loop variable $i = 1 \dots n$. The table shows n/t .

Conclusion: If simplicity and speed are the main arguments, the winner is the Raspberry Pi Pico. WLAN and Bluetooth wireless communication is best realized with the ESP32 board.

¹⁰⁾ The IO-Warrior software reacts only to changes in the status lines, which could not be varied during our test.

¹¹⁾ Arduino Ethernet shield connected via RJ-45 cable to Router, notebook (PC) connected to the same router via WLAN. Attaching also the notebook via Ethernet cable instead of WLAN hardly improves the speed. Nor does connecting shield and PC directly via a RJ-45 cable increase the performance.

Figure 15: Prototype of an Arduino Uno at the bottom plus Ethernet shield on top plus green parallel port interface.

board	interface	firmware emul.	softw. PC	data time/ms	status time/ms
Arduino Nano	USB	C++	C++, boost::asio	0.4	4
Arduino Uno	USB	C++	C++, boost::asio	0.4	4
ESP8266	USB	C++	C++, boost::asio	0.7	3
ESP32	USB	C++	C++, boost::asio	0.7	3
Raspberry Pi Pico	USB	MicroPython	C++, mpremove	300	700
Raspberry Pi Pico	USB	C++	C++, boost::asio	0.2	2
IO-Warrior28	USB	-	C, IO-Warrior-SDK	9	$\ll 1^{10}$
ESP8266	WLAN	C++	C++, curl	20	20
ESP32	WLAN	C++	C++, curl	20	10
ESP32	Bluetooth	C++	C++, system command	150	600
Arduino Uno	Ethernet ¹¹⁾	C++	C++, curl	40	40

Table 2: Benchmark results, obtained with a Dell Vostro 5581 notebook running Ubuntu 22. A USB-2 port was used. The numbers are given in milliseconds per 8-bit access to the data lines (with varying bit patterns) and to the 5 status lines. The serial interface speed was set to 115200 baud. WLAN and Ethernet communications were using a standard web router.

10 Summary and Conclusions

In this paper I advocate the revival of the classical parallel port interface. This standard provides an easy way to set or read bits and thus to control peripheral electronic devices connected to a personal computer. I present several realizations of interfaces – hardware and software – between a PC on the one side and a parallel port device on the other side, using Arduino and Raspberry boards and similar microcontrollers. In the ‘Internet of Things’ and in particular in the ‘Maker’ community this could be of interest.

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References

- [1] Parallel port — Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Parallel_port, retrieved 2024-03-09.
- [2] D-subminiature — Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=D-subminiature>, retrieved 2024-03-09.
- [3] File:Parallel port pinouts.svg — Wikimedia Commons, the free media repository. https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?title=File:Parallel_port_pinouts.svg, retrieved 2024-03-09.
- [4] How do you interface with a USB to Parallel adapter? <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/2609345/how-do-you-interface-with-a-usb-to-parallel-adapter>, retrieved 2024-07-14.
- [5] Henrik Haftmann. USB-zu-Parallel-Umsetzer ”USB2LPT”. <https://www-user.tu-chemnitz.de/~heha/basteIn/PC/USB2LPT/>, retrieved 2024-07-14.
- [6] D. Hebbeker, T. Hebbeker. `paralleport_emulator` (Github). https://github.com/thebbeker/paralleport_emulator.
- [7] Christopher Kohlhoff. Boost.Asio. https://www.boost.org/doc/libs/1_75_0/doc/html/boost_asio.html, retrieved 2024-04-27.
- [8] How do I allow non-root access to /ttyUSB0? <https://askubuntu.com/questions/133235/how-do-i-allow-non-root-access-to-ttyusb0>, retrieved 2024-04-18.
- [9] `dev/ttyUSB0` device connects then is forced to disconnect by another device. <https://askubuntu.com/questions/1454633/dev-ttyusb0-device-connects-then-is-forced-to-disconnect-by-another-device>, retrieved 2024-04-18.
- [10] Downloads Arduino IDE. <https://www.arduino.cc/en/software>, retrieved 2024-03-09.
- [11] SerialEvent. <https://docs.arduino.cc/built-in-examples/communication/SerialEvent/>, retrieved 2024-03-09.
- [12] CodeMagic LTD. WokWi. <https://wokwi.com>, retrieved 2024-04-18.
- [13] Microsoft. Connect USB devices. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/wsl/connect-usb>, retrieved 2024-04-18.

- [14] NodeMCU — Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NodeMCU>, retrieved 2024-03-09.
- [15] Random Nerd Tutorials. Installing ESP8266 NodeMCU Board in Arduino IDE 2. <https://randomnerdtutorials.com/installing-esp8266-nodemcu-arduino-ide-2-0/>, retrieved 2024-03-09.
- [16] curl. <https://github.com/curl/>, retrieved 2024-04-27.
- [17] Random Nerd Tutorials. ESP8266 Pinout Reference. <https://randomnerdtutorials.com/esp8266-pinout-reference-gpios/>, retrieved 2024-03-09.
- [18] Raspberry Pi. MicroPython. <https://www.raspberrypi.com/documentation/microcontrollers/micropython.html>, retrieved 2024-04-18.
- [19] ampy. <https://github.com/scientifichackers/ampy>, retrieved 2024-04-18.
- [20] mpremote. <https://github.com/micropython/micropython/tree/master/tools/mpremote>, retrieved 2024-04-27.
- [21] Random Nerd Tutorials. Programming Raspberry Pi Pico with Arduino IDE. <https://randomnerdtutorials.com/programming-raspberry-pi-pico-w-arduino-ide/>, retrieved 2024-04-18.
- [22] Code Mercenaries. The "Universal" for USB - IO-Warrior. <https://www.codemerics.com/en/io>, retrieved 2024-03-20.
- [23] Visual Studio Code. <https://code.visualstudio.com/>, retrieved 2024-07-14.
- [24] T. Brühlmann. *Arduino Praxiseinstieg*. mitp, Frechen, 2019.
- [25] PC-Direktverbindung per Netzwerk-Kabel. https://wiki.ubuntuusers.de/PC-Direktverbindung_per_Netzwerk-Kabel/, retrieved 2024-05-12.